

TABLE 2—Mo K_α RADIATION

X-ray data of Sm NbO ₄		
dm Å	I/I ₀	hkl
4.624	20	110
3.855	10	101
3.449	15	111
3.193	100	121
3.002	90	040
2.760	20	002
2.689	20	012
2.462	10	220
2.377	15	211
2.272	10	221
2.195	10	151
2.046	15	231, 240
1.932	30	212
1.878	30	161
1.778	20	232
1.654	30	123
1.589	30	170, 133
1.499	15	080
1.353	10	004
1.336	10	024
1.304	20	124

of oxygen atoms, and these tetrahedra run through-out; and can be considered as the binding unit for the entire structural system.

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Aromatic amines as corrosion inhibitor for 63/37 brass in acetic acid solutions

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ALIPHATIC amines, heterocyclic amines and aromatic amines have been extensively studied as corrosion inhibitors of metals and alloys in various media¹⁻⁶. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to evaluate the inhibitive efficiency of aniline and the effect of some groups in the benzene ring of aniline. Following substances were studied: *o*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine and phenetidine.

Experimental

Brass sheets (63/37) were cold rolled and annealed at 550°. It has the following composition

Cu-63.2, Zn-36.6, Sn-0.07 and Pb-0.01%.

Preparation, corrosion testing and cleaning of specimens were same as described before⁷. Each specimen of the size 3×6 cm (26 S.W.G.) was fully immersed in 260 ml. of the solution. All experiments were carried out at 32°-5°. Experiments were performed in 0.5 N acetic acid solution, using various concentrations of the inhibitors.

The duration for exposure was 10 days. Results are represented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The results reveal that *o*-toluidine is a very poor inhibitor, while *o*-phenetidine is an excellent inhibitor. The order of increase in inhibitive power is

p-Anisidine < Aniline < *o*-Toluidine < *o*-phenetidine

According to Mann when metal is introduced into an electrolyte, it becomes -ve charged. Helmholtz's double layer is formed on the surface, the +ve ions of the metal tending to go into solution. H⁺ in the solution can replace the metal ions and ultimately get discharged as hydrogen gas. If the inhibitors form an ionizable salt with the metal in the corrosive acid, there will be positive inhibitor ions which may now replace the +ve metal ions of the double layer. Mann assumed that the salt of an amine will be ionized, the positive charge being concentrated on nitrogen. Thus the inhibitor ion is attracted to the cathodic areas of the metal through nitrogen⁸.

Further, nitrogen in NH₂ and oxygen in -OC₂H₅ and -OCH₃ contain respectively one and two lone pairs of electrons. The lone pair electrons makes such atoms adsorbable at suitable sites over the metal surface.

TABLE 1—63/37 (3×6 cm) BRASS IN 0.5N ACETIC ACID WITH AROMATIC AMINES

Duration : 10 days

Concentration of inhibitor (%)	Loss (mdd)	Inhibition (%)	Concentration of inhibitor (%)	Loss (mdd)	Inhibition (%)
<i>Aniline</i>			<i>p-Anisidine</i>		
0.0	24.1		0.0	24.1	—
0.08	18.4	24	0.005	17.9	26
0.2	14.9	38	0.01	16.7	31
0.4	13.2	45	0.025	13.6	44
0.8	13.1	46	0.05	3.53	85
2.0	15.1	33	0.08	3.03	87
<i>o-Toluidine</i>			<i>p-Phenetidine</i>		
0.08	24.6	—2	0.08	1.97	92
0.2	23.6	2	0.2	1.88	92
0.4	22.8	6	0.4	2.27	91
0.8	21.2	12	0.8	2.58	89
1.9	5.3	78	2.1	3.22	87

In *o*-phenetidine oxygen and nitrogen atoms are attached to adjacent carbon atoms of the benzene ring. Both the atoms may be simultaneously adsorbed by the surface covering a much effective area compared to that covered by a single atom. *p*-Anisidine is a better inhibitor than aniline because of the fact that latter contains oxygen atom which can be more strongly adsorbed by metal surface than nitrogen atom. *o*-Toluidine contains methyl group adjacent to $-\text{NH}_2$. This methyl group acts as a steric hindrance to nitrogen atom being adsorbed to the metallic surface. This explains the poor inhibitive power of the substance.

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p-Substituted aromatic amines as corrosion inhibitors for 63/37 brass in nitric acid

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NITRIC acid is highly corrosive to copper and copper-zinc alloys. The corrosive attack of nitric acid on copper is mainly due to the nitrous acid formed during the reaction between copper and nitric acid. Therefore a substance which prevents the autocatalytic cycle of the formation of nitrous acid would act as a corrosion inhibitor. As aromatic amines can react with nitrous acid they should be able to retard the corrosion of copper and copper-zinc alloys in nitric acid. Orthosubstituted aromatic amines have been previously investigated as corrosion inhibitor for 63/37 brass in nitric acid¹. The present article reports the use of *p*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine and *p*-chloroaniline and *p*-aminobenzoic acid as corrosion inhibitors for 63/37 brass in nitric acid solutions.

Experimental

63/37 brass supplied by Messrs Kamani Metals, Bombay, was used for the study. The preparation of specimens and corrosion tests were carried out as described in earlier publication². The effect of inhibitor concentration and time on inhibitor efficiency is given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The change in potential with time of 63/37 brass in 2.0N